

CHLORALIDES. THE CONDENSATION OF BUTYLCHLORAL WITH α -HYDROXYCARBOXYLIC ACIDS.

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The condensation of butylchloral hydrate with α -hydroxycarboxylic acids in presence of sulphuric acid has been studied in order to compare its behaviour with that of chloral.

The condensation of chloral with α -hydroxycarboxylic acids has been studied by numerous investigators (*vide* Shah and Alimchandani, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 545 for details of references), but the corresponding chloralides derived from butylchloral are little known. In the work described here, an attempt to condense butylchloral hydrate with malic, tartaric, citric, mandelic and benzilic acids has been made.

The general method adopted throughout this work was to dissolve the two components in concentrated sulphuric acid and after 24 hours to pour the mixture on to ice.

Malic, tartaric and citric acids give their corresponding butylchloralides. The behaviour of citric and malic acids in this condensation is similar to that with chloral, Tartaric acid on condensation gives only a small quantity of its butylchloralide, most of the butylchloral hydrate being recovered unchanged. This is in contrast to the behaviour of chloral with this acid. Attempts to get the mono-condensation product are unsuccessful. It may be mentioned here that the yield of the butylchloralides is uniformly inferior compared to the corresponding simple chloralides.

Attempts to get crystalline condensation products from mandelic and benzilic acids were fruitless. This is in conformity with the behaviour of aromatic α -hydroxy acids with chloral (Shah and Alimchandani, *loc. cit.*). The reduction of these butylchloralides by zinc dust and acetic acid as in case of simple chloralides (Shah and Alimchandani, *loc. cit.*) has been tried, but no product could be isolated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Citric Acid Butylchloralide.—Powdered citric acid (25 g.), butylchloral

hydrate (25 g.) were mixed and concentrated sulphuric acid (50 c.c.) slowly added. The substances on shaking dissolved to a brownish solution. The mixture was kept for 24 hours and then poured on to ice; a brownish mass separated which solidified on washing with water. It was collected, dissolved in acetic acid and to the acid solution, concentrated hydrochloric acid added when on keeping a white microcrystalline mass was obtained. Recrystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum benzine, it separated as rhombic crystals, m. p. 187-88°, yield 8 g. (Found: Cl, 30'20. $C_{10}H_{11}O_7Cl_3$ requires Cl, 30'46 per cent).

The citric acid butylchloralide is soluble in hot water and in common organic solvents except chloroform and petroleum benzine.

Malic Acid Butylchloralide.—Malic acid (6 g.), butylchloral hydrate (9 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) were mixed and kept overnight and the reaction mixture worked up as before. The product was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum benzine, m. p. 139°, yield 2-3 g. (Found: Cl, 36'27. $C_8H_9O_5Cl_3$ requires Cl, 36'52 per cent).

Tartaric Acid Butylchloralide.—Tartaric acid (15 g.), butylchloral hydrate (42 g., 2 mols.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (50 c.c.) were mixed and the mixture was kept for 24 hours, poured into ice-cold water when a pasty mass separated, which on repeated washing with water, hardened. The product, thus obtained, was found to be soluble in all common organic solvents, gelatinous mass separating. The crude product was dissolved in ether and petroleum benzine added, when on keeping a white crystalline mass was obtained, m. p. 82-83° (mixed m. p. with butylchloral hydrate). The mother-liquor on removal of the solvent gave a substance which was dried on a porous plate and the dry mass crystallised from acetic acid and then from alcohol as small colourless needles, m. p. 156°, yield 2 g. (Found: Cl, 45'55. $C_{12}H_{12}O_8Cl_6$ requires Cl, 45'78 per cent).

The above condensation was repeated with less amount of butylchloral hydrate with no better results. In subsequent work, the excess of the butylchloral hydrate was removed by treating the crude product with hot water.